

From RANS to LES : Comparison of Simulation Methodologies for the Imperial Front Wing

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Abstract

In the present study, we compare the more widespread pressure based Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes solver (PBS RANS) used in the automotive industry as well as the density based (DBS) RANS solvers to our industrial High Order Wall Resolved Implicit Large Eddy Simulations (Fidelity HO WR iLES) solver. Through this study we demonstrate that HO LES simulations can be performed not only on academic test cases but also on realistic automotive test cases. For this study the Imperial Front Wing (IFW) is used, since it is a realistic F1 front wing configuration that has already been studied experimentally and computationally. Various RANS turbulence models at two different spatial resolutions are compared against our Fidelity HO solver at polynomial orders 2 and 3 as well as against the HO iLES Nektar++ reference CFD results. By analysing the lift, drag, PIV planes downstream and viscous stress magnitude, we show that Fidelity HO can capture the physics of the problem better than the FV RANS solvers which present a certain spread in results inherent to the choice of turbulence model. While this is to be expected, in the present study we also show which metrics are the most sensitive to the choice of the CFD solver. We can thus demonstrate that HO LES simulations are able to give more accurate and consistent results in a reasonable amount of time (≈ 24 h) on modern GPU resources, making it a viable tool for engineers in the future for specific applications.

Introduction

Aerodynamics has become the main performance differentiator in motorsport particularly in F1. The famous statement that "aerodynamics are for people who can't build engines" by Enzo Ferrari no longer applies in an era where "Aero is king". While drag is the main focus in most domains (road cars or other sports such as cycling), in F1 the ability to take corners at over 5g is what distinguishes it from other forms of motorsport. In order to do this, the car must generate huge amounts of downforce (negative lift) while minimizing the effect on the drag. While most of the downforce comes from the underbody of the car, particularly in the latest generation of ground effect cars, we will focus on the front wing of an F1 car since not only does it generate about 25%-40% of a car's downforce [1], it also controls the whole flow downstream and can limit the effect of the open wheel wake on the rest of the car. Since current F1 car wing designs are not available, we will instead use the Imperial Front Wing (IFW) model, which is based on the McLaren 17D from 2003. Previous studies on this geometry have been carried out experimentally by Pegrum [2] and computationally by Buscariolo [3].

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A wide range of different CFD models from low to highest fidelity exist : Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS), Unsteady RANS (URANS), Detached Eddy Simulation (DES), Wall Modelled Large Eddy Simulation (WMLES), Wall Resolved Large Eddy Simulation (WRLES) and finally Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS). As computational resources keep increasing, the higher fidelity methods become available not just for simple 2D academic cases, but even for industrial 3D cases at reasonable Reynolds number.

In order to capture accurately the motion of the large eddies in LES, an adequate spatial and temporal resolution needs to be chosen. While finite volume (FV) methods are the most widely used because of the simplicity, using high-order (HO) polynomials within a cell has the advantage of providing better accuracy with fewer degrees of freedom (DoFs or quadrature points) because of the better convergence properties in a theoretical setting.

In order to show the potential of HO LES on industrial test cases, several factors need to be taken into account : trustworthiness, accuracy, numerical stability, computational cost...

In our case, the Flux Reconstruction algorithm based on Huynh [4] is used. For the temporal time stepping, two main categories exist : explicit time stepping which is easy to implement but restrictive on the the size of the physical time step Δt or implicit time stepping which allows us to use much larger physical time steps but requires an iterative solver. If the iterative solver is fast enough, we can chose a physical time step that matches the physics of the unsteady flow rather than the far more restrictive CFL restriction for explicit solvers and thus march forward in time much faster. To do this we combine the Dual Time Stepping (DTS) method with BDF2 (2nd order Backward Finite Difference) which is unconditionally stable and a h/p multigrid algorithm in order to improve the convergence characteristics of the iterative solver at each physical time step.

Combining the HO Flux Reconstruction scheme with a fast implicit solver should thus help reduce the cost of running LES to an acceptable level such that it becomes a potentially viable tool for a CFD engineer in the future. In this paper present an overview of various CFD methods on the simplified F1 front wing. By comparing the accuracy level at different spatial resolutions (DoF count) and comparing RANS with HO LES, we provide answers to questions such as : "Does HO LES provide significantly better accuracy than FV RANS ?", "Are there significant issues regarding numerical stability (i.e. which parameters should be chosen to guarantee stability) ?", "What is the computational cost of HO LES ?"

1 Case Description

1.1 Wind Tunnel

The experiments were carried out in the 10 x 5 Wind Tunnel in the Department of Aeronautics at Imperial College London [5]. The lower section which was used for the experiment is 20m (length) x 3m (width) x 1.5m (height) and is equipped with a rolling belt and full boundary layer control. Flow uniformity is around 1% and turbulence around 0.25%.

Figure 1: IFW geometry and nomenclature [3]: chord length c (yellow line), ride height h , nose cone (A), Gurney Flap (B), canard (C), endplate (D) and footplate (E)

1.2 Experimental IFW Setup

The setup at Imperial College (see Fig.1) used $h/c = 0.36$ which can be considered a low ride height, with significant ground effect and thus high downforce levels. An inlet velocity of 25m/s and a 1:2 model was used for the experiment. Based on chord length $c = 250\text{mm}$ (full scale model), the Reynolds number for the experiment is $Re = 220'000$ (use $L = c/2 = 125\text{mm}$).

1.3 CFD IFW Domain Setup

For the CFD simulations, a mirror boundary condition was used in $y = 0$ and the dimensions correspond to the full scale model of the IFW. As can be seen in Fig 2, the new dimensions of the domain are 19.56m (length) x 3m (width) x 3m (height).

Figure 2: Computational Domain used for the IFW

NB : However, to match the Re of the experiment, the inlet velocity needs to be decreased from 25m/s to 12.5m/s, since we are using the full scale model rather than the half scale model. In this paper, results at both $Re = 440'000$ and $220'000$ will be shown.

2 Mesh Setup

The general principal of LES is that large eddies are simulated while the behaviour of the small eddies is modelled. In order to represent the motion of these larger eddies, sufficient spatial and temporal resolution is needed. The grid and time step act as implicit spatial and temporal filters. We therefore initially present how we can estimate the length and time scales necessary in order to get a good LES simulation before actually presenting the mesh.

The following meshes are used in this paper :

- HO Mesh with 4.06 million cells (≈ 110 million DoFs at \mathcal{P}_2 and ≈ 260 million DoFs at \mathcal{P}_3)
- Refined FV RANS mesh with ≈ 120 million cells (similar DoF count as HO \mathcal{P}_2)
- Coarse FV RANS mesh with ≈ 32 million cells

3 A-priori RANS Estimation of Length and Time Scales

Before presenting the meshes used, it is useful to go over the length and time scales present in the flow to get an idea of the sizes of eddies and the locations that require refinement. In FV, eddies that are smaller than the cell size cannot be represented since the cell average doesn't contain enough information to represent the swirling motion of the eddy, as shown in Fig. 3. When moving to a HO solver, the information within a cell is represented by a polynomial of order P rather than a cell average value, we therefore choose to apply a scaling factor of $2P+1$ (other scaling factors such as $P+1$ and P^2 are also used).

Regarding the temporal resolution, the size of time step Δt chosen will determine which frequencies in time can be represented. If we wish to represent the fluctuating motion of an eddy (frequency), the Nyquist-Shannon sampling

Figure 3: Illustrating how the mesh determines which eddies are simulated and which are modelled [6](e.g. with an SGS model). The mesh size acts as a filter on the eddies.

theorem tells us that we need at least 2 sampling points in order to represent a certain frequency. With explicit time stepping, the CFL constraint for stability is usually very restrictive, meaning that all frequencies are represented provided the grid resolution is sufficient. For implicit time stepping schemes such as BDF2 which are unconditionally stable, Δt can be however small or large as we want/need. We can thus pick Δt such that it represents the motion of the large eddies while filtering out the motion of the smaller eddies.

However two main questions need to be answered in order to pick a given spatial and temporal resolution :

- What are the sizes of the eddies we wish to represent and how do we estimate them ?
- What is the time scale (of these eddies) that we wish to represent and how do we estimate it ?

To answer these questions we will go back turbulence theory and the energy cascade [8]. In a turbulent flow, the energy cascade describes the distribution of turbulent energy in wavenumber space. Most of the kinetic energy is contained in the large scales, at intermediate scales the eddies break down into smaller eddies, while at the smallest scales dissipation dominates and turns the energy into heat. While not a guarantee of accuracy, as a general rule 80% of turbulent kinetic energy should be resolved to get a good LES simulation.

Figure 4: Energy cascade with the three turbulent characteristic length scales l_0 , λ and η that describe the energy cascade [7]

The energy cascade (see Fig. 4) is defined by three length scales which can be estimated with a RANS computation :

- Integral length scale : $l_0 = \frac{k^{3/2}}{\epsilon}$ ($k - \epsilon$ model) or $l_0 = \frac{\sqrt{k}}{C_\mu \omega}$ (for $k - \omega$ model) defines the largest length scales in the production range
- Taylor length scale (also called Turbulent length scale): $\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{10\nu k}{\epsilon}}$ defines the length scales present in the inertial subrange. Smaller scales start to be affected by molecular viscosity. By dimensional analysis it can be estimated as $\lambda \approx \sqrt{10} Re_L^{-1/2} l_0$
- Kolmogorov length scale : $\eta = \left(\frac{\nu^3}{\epsilon}\right)^{1/4}$ defines the smallest length scales where viscosity dominates and the energy is dissipated into heat. By dimensional analysis it can be estimated as $\eta \approx Re_L^{-3/4} l_0$. This is the resolution required for DNS such that all the scales are simulated.

Therefore we will run a precursor $k - \epsilon$ RANS simulation to plot the Taylor length scale and thus get an estimation of where to place refinement boxes and what mesh size h is required

Similarly to the length scales, the same argument can be made for the various turbulent time scales. They are defined as follows :

- Integral time scale : $\tau_0 = k/\epsilon$
- Taylor time scale : $\tau_\lambda = \left(\frac{15\nu}{\epsilon}\right)^{1/2}$. By dimensional analysis $\tau_\lambda = \sqrt{15} Re_L^{-1/2} \tau_0$
- Kolmogorov time scale : $\tau_\eta = \left(\frac{\nu}{\epsilon}\right)^{1/2}$ This is the temporal resolution required to run a DNS simulation

It is important to remember that eddies require a certain grid resolution and a certain temporal resolution in order to represent their motion. If the grid resolution is increased but the temporal resolution is not, it is possible that the smaller eddies will not be represented and we will therefore get no benefit from increasing the grid resolution (or increasing the polynomial order).

3.1 HO Mesh

In order to generate a good quality HO mesh, a few characteristics need to be achieved. This includes keeping the cell count low in order to benefit from the high order representation within each cell, while at the same time accurately representing the geometry (less of a problem for FV since cell count is higher, hence the use of curved elements). Since we are not using wall modelled LES, the y^+ values should be kept close to 1 for the nearest quadrature point. In order to simulate well the boundary layer, X^+ and Z^+ in the range of 20 should be targeted. While other characteristics are important (e.g. skewness) for stability reasons, the criteria mentioned above are more specifically related to the mesh resolution and therefore related the computational cost which is already higher for LES than RANS.

- Fidelity’s Hexpress mesher
- 2nd order curved elements
- Base mesh size : 0.5m
- Wake cell size : $h = 0.0078125\text{m}$ (refinement level = 6)
- Min. cell size : 1mm
- Boundary Layer (front wing)
 - Total thickness : 3mm (same as Nektar++ paper [3])
 - First layer height : $4.3 \cdot 10^{-5}\text{m}$
 - Number of layers : 7
 - Growth rate : 1.6
- Boundary layer (floor) :
 - Total thickness : 3mm
 - First layer height : 0.0001m
 - Number of layers : 6
 - Growth rate : 1.5
- Finite Volume maximum $y^+ \approx 6$ (leading edge of 1st wing element)
 - Nearest quadrature point at $y^+ \approx 1$ for \mathcal{P}_3
- X^+ and $Z^+ \in [10, 60]$ with the smaller values being near the leading and trailing edges of the wing elements
- Total mesh count : 4.06 million cells (≈ 110 million DoFs at \mathcal{P}_2 and ≈ 260 million DoFs at \mathcal{P}_3)

Figure 5: FV y^+ on HO Mesh : $\max(\text{FV } y^+) \approx 6$

Figure 6: HO Mesh

To justify the choice of the refinement level in the wake, let us firstly estimate the Taylor length scale. If we assume the integral length scale to be $l_0 = 0.25\text{m}$ and use scaling analysis based on $\text{Re} = 440'000$, we obtain $\lambda \approx 1.2\text{mm}$. However by running a RANS $k-\epsilon$ model, we can get an estimate of this Taylor length scale throughout the whole domain. In Fig. 7 we illustrate the Taylor length scale as the flow flows around the wing elements. As can be noted, the initial estimate $\lambda \approx 1.2\text{mm}$ is quite reasonable in the wake of the wing, however further refinement is required underneath the leading edge of the 1st wing element, between the wing elements and near the floor. We notice the mesh size chosen for the wake $h = 7.8125\text{mm} \approx 6.5\lambda$, which when considering the scaling that comes from having quadrature points within each cell indicates that we should have sufficient refinement at \mathcal{P}_3 .

(a) The small turbulent scales are mostly present in the wake, near the floor. We also notice that we need to place a refined box sufficiently high in order to capture the small scales coming off the 3rd wing element.

(b) The area coloured in red should have sufficient spatial refinement with a wake cell size of $h = 7.8125\text{mm}$ at \mathcal{P}_3 . The blue coloured areas (gaps between wing elements and the underside of the 1st wing element) require at least 1 or 2 levels of further mesh refinement.

Figure 7: Slice at $y = -0.4\text{m}$ illustrating the Taylor length scale λ ($\text{Re} = 440'000$)

(a) The main wake refinement area ($h = 7.8125\text{mm}$) necessary to capture $\lambda \approx 1.2\text{mm}$

(b) Additional mesh refinement between the wing elements to capture $\lambda \approx 0.3\text{mm}$

Figure 8: HO Mesh in the neighbourhood of the front wing

Information Regarding the FV RANS meshes are in the Appendix.

4 Simulation Setup

For the simulation, the same boundary conditions (BCs) were used as suggested in [3], which consist in using : Euler slip walls for the external side wall and the ceiling, a mirror BC for the symmetry plane in $y = 0$, an inlet velocity of $U_{inf} = 25\text{m/s}$ ($\text{Re} = 440'000$) or 12.5m/s ($\text{Re} = 220'000$), a moving floor with slip wall set to U_{inf} and a pressure outlet at atmospheric pressure.

4.1 FV RANS Simulation Setup

For the FV RANS models (DBS and PBS) the default options were kept almost everywhere. The turbulent kinetic energy k and turbulent dissipation rate ϵ were set based on the following. The turbulent kinetic energy k can be estimated from the turbulence intensity $I = 0.25\%$ as follows [9] :

$$k = \frac{3}{2}(U_{\infty}I)^2 = 0.0059 \quad (1)$$

Similarly for the turbulence dissipation rate ϵ the following estimation [9] is used :

$$\epsilon = \frac{c_{\mu}^{0.75} \cdot k^{1.5}}{0.07L} \implies \epsilon_{inlet} \approx 8 \cdot 10^{-4} \quad (2)$$

, where $c_{\mu} = 0.09$ and $L = 1.32\text{m}$ is the height of the wind tunnel

5 HO Simulation Setup

For the HO LES simulations, rather conservative CFL numbers were used for the inner iterations and the choice of the physical time step $\Delta t = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s is based on the Taylor Time scales as shown in Fig. 9, which should allow us to capture most of the physics and turbulence except for the smallest eddies in the boundary layer. The following settings were used

Figure 9: The smallest Taylor Time Scales are present on the suction side of the wing element. A value of $\Delta t = 0.00025$ s should capture most of the frequencies.

- Polynomial order : 2 (and 3)
- Time integration : implicit, 200 inner iterations, -2.5 convergence criterion (for residual drop), RKSTR3 scheme for inner iterations
- Physical time step : $\Delta t = 0.00025$ s
- 1 grid level (no h-multigrid)
- Polynomial multigrid (pMG): V-cycle with 1 smoothing step at each polynomial level
- Material : Air Perfect Gas
 - $P_{ref} = 101'325$ Pa, $T_{ref} = 293$ K, dynamic viscosity : $1.716 \cdot 10^{-5}$ Pa.s
- Physics : Laminar flow model (no SGS model)
- Initial solution : Precursor FV RANS
- Numerics :
 - CFL numbers : 0.25 (for the HO modes) and 1 (for \mathcal{P}_0 level)
 - Roe flux
 - Modal filtering : $\alpha = 8$, strength = 36 and cut-off percentage : 80%

Notice that we choose to use 1 smoothing step per polynomial level for the pMG. While carrying out more smoothing steps on the coarser levels per V-cycle should provide significant speed-up, using 1 smoothing step per polynomial level provides far more stable results. This issue deserves more investigation since it is an area where potential computational speed up can be achieved.

6 Results

In this section we mainly present results that can be compared against some other relevant benchmarks. The two benchmarks we compare our results against are the experimental results from the windtunnel and the Nektar++ results [3].

With regards to the experiment, the following is provided :

- PIV Planes : Non-dimensional u_y and u_z velocity components in 5 PIV planes present downstream of the end-plate (Fig. 10)
- Wall shear stress : This was run at lower wind tunnel velocity of 15m/s and also without the moving belt.
- No Lift and Drag values are given

Plane locations for PIV measurements.		
Plane number	X [mm]	X/c [-]
1	-295	-1.176
2	-250	-1.000
3	-150	-0.600
4	-24	-0.096
5	150	0.600

Figure 10: Locations of the 5 PIV Planes [3]

With regards to Nektar++, the following is provided :

- PIV Planes : Non-dimensional u_y and u_z velocity components in 5 PIV planes present downstream of the endplate
- Wall shear stress : This was run at $Re=220'000$ with the moving belt
- Lift and drag coefficient are provided

6.1 Lift and Drag

6.1.1 Lift and Drag : RANS

In Fig. 11 we see the convergence of the drag coefficient for all RANS models on both a coarse and refined mesh. Overall we do not see too much variation and good agreement with the HO LES reference value (dashed blue line). A slight improvement can be noticed when refining the mesh but it remains minor.

Figure 11: Drag coefficient convergence for all RANS models at $Re = 440'000$. Reference Fidelity HO LES \mathcal{P}_3 at $Re = 440'000$ is given as a dashed blue line.

In Fig. 12 we see the convergence of the lift coefficient for all the RANS models on both coarse and refined mesh. Overall we see that RANS predicts smaller downforce values than the reference HO result across all models. This gap appears to have somewhat decreased with the more refined mesh but it nevertheless remains noticeable. In both Fig. 11 and 12, we notice that restarting the EARSM from the Spalart Allmaras appears to cause a jump. This simulation should probably be re-run, but this time by initialising from a uniform field like the others. In Table 1 we summarise the lift and drag coefficients obtained on both meshes for the various RANS models and compute an average and standard deviation across all RANS models.

Figure 12: Lift coefficient convergence for all RANS models at $Re = 440'000$. Reference Fidelity HO LES \mathcal{P}_3 at $Re = 440'000$ is given as a dashed blue line.

FV RANS Models				
FV RANS Simulations	Drag coeff. (120M DoFs)	Drag coeff. (32M DoFs)	Lift coeff. (120M DoFs)	Lift coeff. (32M DoFs)
DBS EARSM (Re = 440'000)	0.587	0.598	-5.38	-5.42
DBS $k - \omega$ SST (Re = 440'000)	0.603	0.606	-5.66	-5.57
DBS $k - \epsilon$ (Re = 440'000)	0.597	0.600	-5.78	-5.38
DBS Spalart All. (Re = 440'000)	0.598	0.608	-5.58	-5.54
PBS EARSM (Re = 440'000)	0.609	0.614	-5.70	-5.56
PBS $k - \omega$ SST (Re = 440'000)	0.611	0.617	-5.75	-5.64
PBS RSM (Re = 440'000)	0.601	0.607	-5.70	-5.56
FV RANS (avg. all models)	0.601 ± 0.007	0.607 ± 0.006	-5.65 ± 0.13	-5.54 ± 0.08

Table 1: Summary of all lift and drag coefficients obtained with the RANS models

6.1.2 Lift and Drag : HO LES

The lift and drag coefficients obtained at $Re = 440'000$ are presented here. After using a steady FV RANS on the HO mesh (4.06 million cells), a transient phase appears where the lift and drag change significantly before reaching something resembling a statistically stationary state. In a statistically stationary state, the probability distribution is time invariant (i.e the moving average and variance should not change in time). We also expect the histogram to look like a Gaussian distribution. A post-processing script to determine the statistics of the coefficients was written outside of Fidelity. This allows us to track the moving average (with a user defined window size), the Savitzky-Golay filter which smooths the data similarly to the moving average and a histogram which shows the distribution of the coefficients within a user defined window. This should allow us to judge whether the averaging window that we have selected respects the characteristics that we expect from a statistically stationary state and also to get an error estimate on the coefficients. If we reach a statistically stationary state, we can use the variance as our error estimator (or to give a confidence interval). However if the moving average is still changing (transient), the variance underestimates the true error, since it doesn't distinguish fluctuations from changes in mean value. The basic theory for confidence interval computation assumes that you have X as a random sample from a given probability distribution. However during a transient the probability distribution is still changing and the current statistics (mean and variance) at the present simulation time will not be the same as you progress in time.

(a) Evolution of the drag coefficient over the whole simulation (transient and time averaging). The averaging is done over the last 12.5CTUs (after the vertical black line)

(b) Evolution of the drag during the averaging window and the moving average (window size of 200 time steps) on the left. Histogram of the drag coefficient during the averaging window on the right. A much larger sample size would be required to get a Gaussian distribution.

Figure 13: Analysis of the drag coefficient at $Re = 440'000$ at P2 ($\#DoFs \approx 110$ millions) : $C_D = 0.597 \pm 0.004$ after 12.5CTUs of averaging

In Fig. 13a and 14a we see the evolution of the drag and lift coefficient over a full simulation of about 29 CTUs at \mathcal{P}_2 at $Re = 440'000$. It can be seen that it takes about 17 CTUs for both lift and drag to flatten out and converge towards a mean value. When we zoom in to the last 12.5 CTUs

which represents the averaging window we choose, we notice that the moving average (window size of 200 time steps) and the Savitzky-Golay filter only fluctuates slightly for drag (Fig. 13b) while it is still moving downwards slightly for lift (Fig. 14b). This indicates that our error estimate for the lift coefficient should be a bit larger than the variance. However given that we do not have a good alternative for the error estimator without running until the results converge, we will simply state that it is underestimated slightly.

(a) Evolution of the lift coefficient over the whole simulation (transient and time averaging). The averaging is done over the last 12.5CTUs (after the vertical black line)

(b) Evolution of the lift during the averaging window and the moving average (window size of 200 time steps) on the left. Histogram of the drag coefficient during the averaging window on the right. A much larger sample size would be required to get a Gaussian distribution.

Figure 14: Analysis of the lift coefficient at $Re = 440'000$ at \mathcal{P}_2 ($\#DoFs \approx 110$ millions) : $C_L = -6.045 \pm 0.010$ after 12.5CTUs of averaging

The figures for \mathcal{P}_3 at $Re = 440'000$ and those for \mathcal{P}_2 at $Re = 220'000$ are in the Appendix. In Table 2 we summarise all the coefficients obtained

High Fidelity Aerodynamic Coefficients		
Simulation	Drag coeff.	Lift coeff.
Experiment	not available	not available
Nektar++ P4 ($Re = 220'000$)	0.568	-5.3
Nektar++ P5 ($Re = 220'000$)	0.575	-5.54
Fidelity HO P2 ($Re = 440'000$)	0.597 ± 0.004	-6.045 ± 0.01
Fidelity HO P3 ($Re = 440'000$)	0.594 ± 0.003	-6.043 ± 0.012
Fidelity HO P2 ($Re = 220'000$)	0.594 ± 0.004	-5.809 ± 0.01

Table 2: Table summarising all the LES lift and drag coefficients at various Reynolds.

The main observations when comparing the LES and RANS lift and drag results are :

- Running the case at a lower Reynolds seems to mainly influence the lift coefficient (about 4%) and not so much the drag coefficient (see Table 2).
- Increasing the number of DoFs (32M to 120M) for the RANS simulations decreases the gap between the RANS and the Fidelity HO LES predictions. The difference is more noticeable for lift (Fig. 11 and 12).
- Negligible difference when increasing from the polynomial order from \mathcal{P}_2 to \mathcal{P}_3 in Fidelity (see Table 2) for both lift and drag.
- Less variability in predicting the drag coefficient than the lift coefficient between solvers. At $Re = 440'000$, there is about 1% difference between Fidelity HO (P2 & P3) and the average across all RANS models ($C_D(avg.RANS) = 0.601 \pm 0.007$ vs $C_D(HO P_3) = 0.594 \pm 0.03$). However for lift this difference is about 6.5% ($C_L(avg.RANS) = -5.65 \pm 0.13$ vs $C_L(HO P_3) = -6.043 \pm 0.012$).
- PBS RANS solvers converge extremely fast towards a given coefficient, DBS RANS require far more iterations, while LES simulations require about 15CTUs to begin to converge.

- The difference with the Nektar++ results can be explained by two factors :
 - Most of our simulations were ran at a higher Reynolds number. By decreasing the Re to 220'000 we did observe a drop in the lift coefficient magnitude at \mathcal{P}_2 (from $C_L(Re = 440'000) = -6.045 \pm 0.01$ to $C_L(Re = 220'000) = -5.809 \pm 0.01$)
 - The Nektar++ simulation time was shorter (about 12 CTUs) : the lift coefficient in particular requires a longer simulation time to reach a statistically stationary state.

Without experimental values, it is still uncertain which can be considered the most reliable since there are differences amongst the LES methods. However by looking at the PIV planes and the wall shear stress and comparing those results we can evaluate the trustworthiness of the LES solvers.

6.2 PIV Planes

While getting accurate lift and drag coefficient are essential, it is possible to get a good drag/lift value with a bad CFD simulation (e.g. over predicting drag on some surfaces and under predicting on others can lead to a reasonable overall force but for the wrong reasons). For this reason it is important to accurately predict the flow physics. If the flow physics is correct, then when know that our lift and drag coefficients are reliable for the right reasons. A solver that captures the flow physics better might not necessarily give a more accurate C_D or C_L , but the value given can be considered more trustworthy. To verify the accuracy of the flow physics we will be comparing the y and z component of velocity at several PIV planes downstream of the endplate. All the Fidelity PIV plane results shown below are at $Re = 440'000$.

In Fig. 21a, we see the V_y component of velocity in the 1st PIV plane. In general all the solvers overpredict an inwards movement of the flow (red circle in the bottom left corner) compared to the experiment. This is systematic across all the FV RANS, Fidelity HO LES and Nektar++ to a lesser extent. This could be caused by an incorrect prediction of the footplate vortex, but further investigation would be necessary. We can however confirm that it is not Reynolds number related, since this overprediction is seen at $Re = 440'000$ and $Re = 220'000$ (not shown here). Another area with some noticeable differences is in the bottom right corner, where the RANS results generally predict a thicker shear layer. This is also present in the Fidelity LES, but is less noticeable.

Figure 15: PIV Plane 1 : Normalized V_y ($y \in [-690\text{mm}, -400\text{mm}]$ and $z \in [0\text{mm}, 285\text{mm}]$)

In Fig. 16 we compare the various plots in the 5th PIV plane, where we observe four main differences. Firstly at the top left corner (circled in red), we notice a vortex that is completely diffused downstream in most RANS results (except PBS RSM and to a lesser degree also DBS $k - \epsilon$) but not for LES. Secondly we notice a negative velocity component near the floor (dashed red circle) that is also present in most RANS results but not in the LES ones. Thirdly for PBS RSM and DBS $k - \epsilon$, we notice what appears to be an additional vortex (circled in black) which is almost completely diffused in the experiment, in the LES results and in the other RANS results. Finally we notice some differences in the strength of the largest vortex structure. We observe that HO \mathcal{P}_2 does the best job, while Nektar++ and Fidelity \mathcal{P}_3 appear to be more diffused.

Figure 16: PIV Plane 5: Normalised V_y : The three most noticeable differences are circled

In Fig. 17 we see the V_z velocity component in the 5th PIV plane. Overall we notice, as expected, more diffused vortices for the RANS models despite having similar spatial resolution as HO \mathcal{P}_2 . This underlines that solving for the temporal unsteadiness is necessary to get the correct magnitude. We also notice more variation across the LES solutions. However as vortices move downstream, we expect differences already present in the 1st PIV plane to increase in size.

Figure 17: PIV Plane 5: Normalised V_z : Vortices are generally far more diffused for the RANS models (except DBS $k - \epsilon$ and PBS RSM)

6.3 Wall Shear Stress

The visualisation of the wall shear stress allows us to understand the flow features near the surface of the geometry. We can thus identify flow separation caused by adverse pressure gradient. When the flow separates, the sign of the wall shear stress changes from positive to negative. A separation point is thus defined by a zero magnitude wall shear stress.

Figure 18: Wall shear stress magnitude (non-dimensional units) on pressure side (top view).

In Fig. 18 we see the wall shear stress magnitude on the pressure side (top view) for the various solvers. Since Nektar++ uses non-dimensional units, the colour scaling was adjusted for the Fidelity figures. Generally the first two wing elements don't present significant differences across all solutions. For the third wing element, the LES and $k - \epsilon$ model appear to show streaks, which are not present in the other RANS results. On the canard, the RANS models don't highlight the low shear patches (coloured in blue) on the canard as well as LES, except for the $k - \epsilon$ model where this feature is more pronounced.

Figure 19: Wall shear stress magnitude (non-dimensional units) on suction side (bottom view). RANS models do not predict the flow separation unlike the LES models. NB : all Fidelity results are at $Re = 440'000$, Nektar++ at $Re = 220'000$ and experiment at $Re = 132'000$. Fidelity HO LES wall shear stress at $Re = 220'000$ are shown in Fig. 20.

In Fig. 19, the wall shear stress on the suction side (bottom view) is illustrated and the differences are far more noticeable. None of the RANS models appear to predict the separation on any of the wing elements. The streaky features present in the experiment and the LES results are also not present in any of the RANS models. When comparing the Fidelity results to the Nektar++, we notice much more details in the Nektar++ results at \mathcal{P}_5 most likely because of the increased spatial and temporal resolution. The $\Delta t = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s chosen for the implicit solver in

Fidelity HO is too large to capture some of the smaller Taylor time scales in the boundary layer which Nektar++ captures because it uses a IMEX temporal splitting scheme. In [3] and in Fig. 20, the Nektar++ results at \mathcal{P}_3 and \mathcal{P}_4 are also shown and appear to confirm that very high spatial resolution is required since the re-attachment is not predicted correctly for Nektar++ at \mathcal{P}_3 .

Figure 20: Illustrating the various LES results at different Reynolds. When increasing the polynomial order we notice a very significant improvement in the finer structures.

In Fig. 20 we only illustrate the LES results and add our HO \mathcal{P}_2 results at $\text{Re}=220'000$. As can be seen, the colour mapping matches much better with the Nektar++ results on the leading edge of all three wing elements (red strip is more noticeable) and the separation line appears to be more in line with Nektar++'s prediction. However once again the spatial resolution is not sufficient to capture the same amount of detail as Nektar++ (\mathcal{P}_5).

6.4 Low to High Fidelity Transition

In a world where FV RANS is a well known method albeit with its limitations, justifying the usage of LES can be a challenge in an industrial context. Moving from FV to HO adds an additional degree of computational complexity which needs to be justified by better accuracy and better consistency (i.e. no inherent variability caused by the choice of the turbulence model). In this section we wish to illustrate the benefit of moving from a coarse FV mesh (32M cells) to a fine FV mesh (120M cells) to a HO LES at \mathcal{P}_2 and finally to a HO LES at \mathcal{P}_3 and compare them with the two benchmarks available (experiment and Nektar++ \mathcal{P}_5). This should show that while better accuracy can be achieved with RANS by increasing the number of DoFs, actually simulating the unsteadiness in LES is necessary to capture certain features. For readability purposes we will only use the DBS $k - \omega$ SST model.

In Fig. 21a we see the normalised V_y velocity component in the first PIV plane. A significant improvement in the shape and diffusion level of the vortices can be noticed when moving from the coarse to the fine FV mesh. The difference between FV RANS (120M cells) and both HO (\mathcal{P}_2 and \mathcal{P}_3) results are less noticeable except for the area near the floor circled with a dashed red line, where a thicker shear layer appears to have formed caused by the inwards movement of the flow. The main area that is not predicted well by any of our simulations is the inwards moving flow under the footplate circled in red. This area is over predicted in Nektar++ and significantly over predicted by our HO LES and RANS results. This could be caused by the footplate vortex, but without further experimental data, it is hard to determine.

(a) Normalised V_y : The main difference comes from the inwards moving flow ($V_y \approx +1$) underneath the footplate as circled in red. Another area with noticeable differences is the area near the floor where a thickening shear layer appears to have been created.

(b) Normalised V_z : Incorrectly predicted feature circled in red disappears when moving from RANS to LES

Figure 21: PIV Plane 1 : ($y \in [-690\text{mm}, -400\text{mm}]$ and $z \in [0\text{mm}, 285\text{mm}]$)

In Fig. 21b we see the normalised V_z velocity component in the first PIV plane. When comparing the two FV RANS solutions, we notice that while the refined mesh does a better job at predicting the magnitude of canard and top vortex, the situation is somewhat less clear for the main vortex. In fact we notice that the refined mesh appears to have a new feature circled in red. When moving to the LES simulations, this features disappear and there is very good agreement across all the LES results and the experiment.

7 Discussion

In this section, we will briefly go over one particular difference in the PIV planes. When observing all the normalised V_y velocity components (see Appendix), we noticed initially a thin shear layer on the bottom right corner that gradually gets thicker as we move from PIV plane 1 (Fig. 29) to PIV plane 2 (Fig. 31) to PIV plane 3 (Fig. 33) for all RANS models and also for Fidelity HO to a lesser extent. Further downstream, we observe that for the RANS results a secondary vortex is produced (dashed green circle in Fig. 16 and Fig. 35) near the floor. This phenomenon is illustrated in Fig. 22 and explained in more detail by Pegrum [2].

If we were to carry out the simulations again, more spatial resolution would be used on the moving floor just under and a few chord lengths behind the IFW to see whether this phenomenon can be mitigated by higher mesh resolution.

Figure 22: Illustration [2] of the creation of a secondary vortex as a consequence of the viscous interaction between a vortex and a solid boundary.

8 Hardware & Execution Time

When talking about the drawbacks of LES over RANS, the main hurdle is execution time necessary to run the simulation. Therefore we will briefly illustrate how we can achieve a simulation time of ≈ 24 hours on current resources for the IFW test case. The hardware that was used was 1 GPU node (CPU : 2X AMD EPYC 75F3, 64 cores ; GPU 8x NVIDIA A100, 80GB SXM4) for the HO \mathcal{P}_2 simulation. Since we are using an implicit solver, the number of inner iterations per physical time step is what determines the execution time. We had **$\approx 2.4s$ /inner iteration for 110M DOfs on 1 GPU node**. If we require 125 time steps for the transient phase of 0.125s ($\Delta t = 0.001s$), 500 time steps for the averaging phase of 0.125s ($\Delta t = 0.00025s$) and we use 150 inner iterations per time step, this would result in 93'750 inner iterations which would take $\approx 62h$ on 1 GPU node. Considering we have 4 GPU nodes available, with an estimated speed of a factor 2.9x, when we can estimate a **total wall clock time of approximately 22h on 4 GPU nodes (for 25 CTUs)**.

9 Next Steps

In order to bridge the gap between High Order Wall Resolved LES (HO WRLES) and FV RANS, the next logical step would be to add Detached Eddy simulation results and Wall Modelled LES (WMLES) results. Preliminary simulations are being carried out at the present time with the WMLES CharLES solver on this test case. Within the context of the SSeCoID [10] Project sponsored by the EU Horizon 2020 programme, further experimental data should be provided by McLaren regarding the front wing.

Conclusion

In this study we went over different CFD tools that can be used to simulate the flow around a realistic F1 front wing configuration. We were thus able to verify the benefits of moving from FV RANS to High Order Flux Reconstruction LES by comparing the viscous stress on the wing elements, the lift and drag coefficients as well as the vortices generated by the endplate as they propagate downstream.

Since F1 is subject to restrictions on CFD and wind tunnel testing, it is essential that the updates provided can bring to the track the performance gains predicted by CFD. Drag and downforce are obviously the two main factors to measure the lap time gains for a design update. Reliable predictions of lift and drag are thus essential.

Regarding the prediction of the drag coefficient, we can refer to Table 1 and 2, where we observe that all the solvers predict similar enough values. The difference between our LES simulations and the RANS models at similar DoF count (120 million cells) and with a lower DoF count (32 million cells) are around 1%, while the difference with the Nektar++ (\mathcal{P}_5) results are a bit more significant (around 3.5%). Despite our LES simulation running for significantly more CTUs, it is not possible to say with certainty whether this drag coefficient should change significantly.

On the other hand, the lift predictions have far more variance. When comparing our LES results we notice a negligible difference when increasing the polynomial order, but we do notice a clearly quantifiable difference when comparing the results at $\text{Re} = 440'000$ and $220'000$. The average FV RANS lift coefficient (at $\text{Re} = 440'000$) is about 6.5% off what the Fidelity HO LES predicts at the same Reynolds. The final Nektar++ (\mathcal{P}_5 at $\text{Re} = 220'000$) $C_L = -5.54$ is significantly lower in magnitude ($\approx 4.7\%$) than $C_L = -5.81$ which is what we obtained at $\text{Re} = 220'000$. Unlike the drag coefficient, the lift coefficient requires more CTUs to converge. We can thus expect this 4.7% difference to decrease for longer simulation time.

The PIV measurements downstream of the endplate are an interesting benchmark for CFD solvers for two main reasons. Firstly, the endplates are essential in redirecting the flow around the exposed front wheels of an F1 car such that the aerodynamics on the rest of the F1 works optimally. Secondly the complexity of the endplates generates far more complicated flow features to predict. It is therefore more challenging for the solver than the rest of the wing which are inverted airfoils.

The most noticeable observations when analysing the PIV plane results (section 6.2), is the variation across all RANS models especially the further downstream we are (Fig 17 or Appendix). Most of the RANS models have vortices that are far more diffused than in the experiment or the LES, except DBS $k - \epsilon$ and PBS RSM. Some of the RANS models even appear to present vortices that are not present in the experiment or the LES (Fig. 16). Because of this significant variation, choosing an appropriate turbulence model for RANS is essential. Since none of the models consistently does a better job than the other (vortex locations, vortex diffusion downstream, etc...), choosing a good RANS model seems impossible. When comparing the LES results (Nektar++ and Fidelity HO) with the experiment, we generally see much better agreement. The main difference comes from the V_y component of velocity just below the endplate (see Fig. 15), where we notice the Fidelity HO is quite far off the experiment, with Nektar++ giving a result that is half way between the experiment and Fidelity HO. Further downstream the LES results do a decent job at predicting the location, strength and shape of the vortices.

When observing the wall shear stress, all the solvers provide similar enough results on the pressure side of the wing elements since the flow remains attached. On the suction side however, large differences appear. All the RANS models fail to predict the laminar separation bubble on the first wing element. On the other hand the LES results all predict this separation. We do notice a difference in the location when comparing the Fidelity \mathcal{P}_2 results at $\text{Re} = 440'000$ and $\text{Re} = 220'000$. The features for Fidelity \mathcal{P}_2 at $\text{Re} = 220'000$ resembling the Nektar++ one far more as would be expected. Overall the Nektar++ results show much more detailed structures, which is to be expected since the spatial (\mathcal{P}_5) and temporal resolution (Nektar++ uses a IMEX temporal splitting scheme with much lower Δt) are higher for Nektar++ in this part of the domain. The flowviz paint for the experiment also shows this separation bubble on the suction side of the 1st wing element. However a good comparison is more difficult to make since the moving belt was turned off and the inlet velocity was also lower. The fact that the LES models in general do a better job at predicting this flow separation on the 1st wing element in particular could well explain why the difference between RANS and LES is more significant for the lift coefficient.

Overall we can conclude that High Order LES simulations are more reliable and present less variability than FV RANS in predicting the flow downstream of an F1 front wing, which is essential for the interaction with the tyres and the rest of the car. They also provide far more consistent, reliable and detailed predictions of the flow features in the near wall area, particularly the suction side of the wing element where the flow separates. Since this is the part of the wing that generates the downforce, accurate prediction of flow separation is essential to measure the cornering performance that a wing design can provide.

Appendix

A Mesh Setup : FV RANS Meshes

Meshes			
Mesh Option	HO Mesh	Refined FV Mesh 3	Coarse FV Mesh
Base mesh size	0.5m	0.125m	0.25m
Wake Cell Size	7.8125mm	1.95mm	3.91mm
Min Cell Size	1mm	0.2mm	0.5mm
IFW Surface			
1st layer thickness	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-5}\text{m}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{m}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-5}\text{m}$
Number of layers	8	18	30
Growth Rate	1.6	1.4	1.3
Refinement Level	6	7	7
h	7.81mm	0.977mm	1.95mm
y^+	≈ 1 at \mathcal{P}_3	< 0.7	< 3
x^+	$\approx [10,60]$ at \mathcal{P}_3	$\approx [30, 100]$	$\approx [80, 200]$
z^+	$\approx [10,60]$ at \mathcal{P}_3	$\approx [30, 100]$	$\approx [80, 200]$
Floor			
1st layer thickness	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}\text{m}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}\text{m}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}\text{m}$
Number of layers	6	20	20
Growth Rate	1.5	1.3	1.6
y^+	≈ 1	< 6	< 6
Total Mesh Count	4.06M cells	120M cells	32M cells

(a) Max y^+ on the moving is ≈ 6

(b) $y^+ < 0.7$ on the IFW surface

Figure 23: y^+ on Refined FV Mesh

(a) Refined FV Mesh

(b) Coarse FV Mesh

Figure 24: Refinement around the wing elements

B HO Lift and Drag

Figure 25: Analysis of the drag coefficient at $Re = 440'000$ at \mathcal{P}_3 ($\#DoFs \approx 260$ millions) after restarting from the \mathcal{P}_2 solution

Figure 26: Analysis of the lift coefficient at $Re = 440'000$ at \mathcal{P}_3 ($\#DoFs \approx 260$ millions) after restarting from the \mathcal{P}_2 solution

(a) Evolution of the drag coefficient over the whole simulation (transient and time averaging). The averaging is done over the last 5CTUs (after the vertical black line)

(b) Evolution of the drag during the averaging window and the moving average (window size of 200 time steps) on the left. Histogram of the drag coefficient during the averaging window on the right.

Figure 27: Analysis of the drag coefficient at $Re = 220'000$ at P2 ($\#DoFs \approx 110$ millions) : $C_D = 0.593 \pm 0.003$ after 5CTUs of averaging

(a) Evolution of the lift coefficient over the whole simulation (transient and time averaging). The averaging is done over the last 5CTUs (after the vertical black line)

(b) Evolution of the lift during the averaging window and the moving average (window size of 50 time steps) on the left. Histogram of the drag coefficient during the averaging window on the right.

Figure 28: Analysis of the lift coefficient at $Re = 220'000$ at P2 ($\#DoFs \approx 110$ millions) : $C_L = -5.800 \pm 0.010$ after 5CTUs of averaging

C PIV Planes

Figure 29: PIV Plane 1: Normalised V_y

Figure 30: PIV Plane 1: Normalised V_z

Figure 31: PIV Plane 2: Normalised V_y

Figure 32: PIV Plane 2: Normalised V_z

Figure 33: PIV Plane 3: Normalised V_y

Figure 34: PIV Plane 3: Normalised V_z

Figure 35: PIV Plane 4: Normalised V_y

Figure 36: PIV Plane 4: Normalised V_z

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